

Social Media Management Practices in Government Bureaucracy: A Strategic Communication Analysis of the Civil Service Police Unit (Satpol PP) of East Java Province

Haris Hanan¹, Zainal Abidin Ahmad², Heidy Arviani³

^{1,2,3} Master of Communication, Faculty of Social, Cultural, and Political Sciences, Universitas Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" Jawa Timur

ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze social media management practices within the Civil Service Police Unit (Satpol PP) of East Java Province in the context of government strategic communication. Using an exploratory qualitative approach, the research examines bureaucratic dynamics, the understanding of key stakeholders, and the implementation of communication strategies in managing social media. Data were collected through in-depth interviews with five key informants and analyzed using thematic analysis techniques. The findings indicate that social media management is still dominated by information dissemination (broadcasting) functions, with limitations in terms of dialogue and public collaboration. A hierarchical bureaucratic structure slows down the content production process, while limited communication competencies among administrators weaken strategic planning. These findings suggest a tension between the demands of adaptive digital communication and rigid bureaucratic structures. This study contributes to the development of government communication research by emphasizing the importance of integrating strategic communication, organizational governance, and digital adaptation.

KEYWORDS: Strategic Communication, Government Social Media, Bureaucracy, Government Public Relations, Digital Governance

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of digital technology has significantly transformed the practice of public communication, particularly within the governmental sector. Social media is no longer merely a channel for information dissemination but has evolved into a participatory space that enables two-way interaction between government and citizens (Bertot et al., 2012; Rahmanto, 2022). In this context, governments are required to manage social media strategically to enhance transparency, public participation, and the quality of public information services. Digital transformation has fundamentally reshaped how governments communicate with society, positioning social media as an essential component of e-government and open government practices.

The utilization of social media by government institutions in Indonesia has increased significantly in line with the rapid growth of internet penetration. Data indicate a substantial rise in internet and social media users, which has consequently driven the adoption of digital platforms as primary channels for public communication (APJII, 2024; We Are Social, 2025). Social media is not only used to disseminate information but also serves as a tool for building institutional image and strengthening relationships between government and citizens (Nabila Ulayya et al., 2022). Moreover, media plays a crucial role in shaping social reality and public opinion through selective issue framing and information dissemination (Bertot et al., 2012)

However, the adoption of social media within government bureaucracies does not always align with the dynamic nature of digital communication. Hierarchical organizational structures and complex administrative procedures often hinder the development of responsive and adaptive communication practices (Criado & Villodre, 2022). This condition creates a paradox between the demand for fast and flexible digital communication and the inherently rigid and slow nature of bureaucratic systems. On the other hand, the use of social media by governments is also considered part of good governance, particularly in providing accessible and high-quality information to the public (Mansoor, 2021).

The Civil Service Police Unit (Satpol PP) as a regional government institution is primarily responsible for enforcing local regulations and maintaining public order and safety. In carrying out its functions, the Satpol PP of East Java Province has adopted social media as a means of public communication through various platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, TikTok, and YouTube. Interestingly, as a provincial-level institution that primarily focuses on coordination and supervision, Satpol PP does not directly

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interact with the public in day-to-day service delivery. This makes the existence and use of social media within the organization a compelling subject of inquiry, particularly in terms of its relevance, objectives, and effectiveness.

Previous studies have shown that effective government social media management requires strategic planning, implementation, monitoring, and continuous evaluation (Putri Pratiwi & Sufyan Abdurrahman, 2021). Additionally, government regulations, such as the Regulation of the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform No. 83 of 2012, emphasize the importance of strategic approaches in social media management, including the application of the People-Objectives-Strategy-Technique (POST) framework. Within this framework, government public relations functions as a communication manager responsible for delivering information in a persuasive, effective, and efficient manner. However, in practice, not all government institutions possess well-established public relations structures, resulting in suboptimal social media management (Sani et al., 2020).

In the case of Satpol PP East Java, social media management demonstrates unique organizational dynamics. The social media team does not entirely consist of individuals with public relations backgrounds and often performs these responsibilities as additional tasks beyond their primary duties. Furthermore, the process of content production and publication must go through multiple layers of bureaucratic approval, which potentially hinders the flexibility and responsiveness of digital communication. This condition raises critical questions regarding whether the use of social media by Satpol PP represents a strategic adaptation to digital transformation or merely a reactive response to emerging technological trends.

Although studies on government social media have been widely conducted, most focus on institutions with well-established communication structures. Research examining social media management practices in institutions lacking formal public relations functions and operating within complex bureaucratic systems remains limited. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the practice of social media management in the Satpol PP of East Java Province.

Specifically, this study seeks to answer two main research questions: (1) how do bureaucratic mechanisms influence social media management, and (2) how do stakeholders perceive and understand the role of social media as a tool for public communication? This research is expected to contribute to the development of government communication studies, particularly in understanding social media management within complex bureaucratic structures, while also providing practical insights for developing more adaptive, participatory, and effective digital communication strategies.

II. METHOD

This study employs a qualitative research method to explore the practice of social media management within the Civil Service Police Unit (Satpol PP) of East Java Province. A qualitative approach is considered appropriate as the research focuses on complex social phenomena that cannot be measured quantitatively and are closely related to human interaction and organizational processes (Strauss & Corbin, 1999; Suyanto & Sutinah, 2022). The study adopts an exploratory design to gain in-depth understanding of how social media is managed within a bureaucratic context, particularly in an institution that does not possess a formal public relations structure (Utama, 2009; Yulibag & Pramono, 2017).

Research Subjects and Sampling Method

The subjects of this study consist of employees of Satpol PP East Java who are directly involved in managing the institution's social media and are part of the public relations team. The participants were selected using purposive sampling, which allows the researcher to intentionally choose individuals who possess relevant knowledge and experience related to the research topic (Campbell et al., 2020).

A total of five informants were selected, representing different organizational roles, ranging from operational staff to mid-level and senior officials. These informants were chosen based on their involvement in social media management and their access to the internal processes of content production and decision-making. This selection ensures that the data reflects both operational and managerial perspectives.

Data Collection Techniques

Data were collected through three main techniques:

1. In-depth Interviews

In-depth interviews were conducted to obtain detailed insights into participants' perceptions, experiences, and understanding of social media management. This method allows the researcher to explore hidden or implicit information and provides flexibility in capturing individual perspectives (Rofiah & Bungin, 2021). The interview guide was developed based on the Regulation of the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform No. 83 of 2012, covering aspects such as content planning, organizational structure, communication objectives, interaction with the public, and evaluation practices.

2. Document Analysis

Document analysis was conducted to complement interview data by examining relevant institutional documents, policies, official publications, and digital content related to social media practices. This method helps provide contextual understanding and supports data triangulation.

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3. Participant Observation

Participant observation was carried out to directly observe social media practices and organizational interactions. This approach allows the researcher to capture real-life behaviors and social dynamics beyond verbal statements, aligning with the principle of “human as instrument” in qualitative research (Lincoln & Guba, 1995). Through observation, the researcher gains deeper insights into how meaning is constructed within the organizational context (Jackson, 1983).

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using thematic analysis, which is a qualitative method used to identify, analyze, and report patterns or themes within data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This approach is flexible and allows for both descriptive and interpretative analysis of qualitative data.

The analysis process followed six stages as proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006):

1. Familiarization with the data through repeated reading
2. Generating initial codes
3. Searching for potential themes
4. Reviewing and refining themes
5. Defining and naming themes
6. Producing the final report

Through this process, raw data were systematically transformed into meaningful patterns that reflect the core findings of the study

Research Procedure

The research was conducted in several stages, including preparation, data collection, data analysis, validation, and reporting. During the preparation stage, interview instruments were developed and informants were identified. The data collection stage involved conducting interviews, observations, and document review. Data were then coded and categorized into thematic findings, followed by validation through triangulation. The final stage involved compiling the findings into a structured academic report.

Validity & Trustworthiness

To ensure the validity and trustworthiness of the findings, this study applied triangulation techniques by combining multiple data sources and methods, including interviews, observations, and document analysis (Lincoln & Guba, 1995). Triangulation helps verify the consistency of findings and minimizes bias from a single perspective, thereby strengthening the credibility of the research.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Strategic Communication in Government

Strategic communication refers to the purposeful use of communication by organizations to achieve their goals (Hallahan et al., 2007). In the context of government, strategic communication functions not only as a tool for disseminating information but also as a mechanism to build public trust, manage reputation, and foster citizen engagement. It involves several key components, including audience analysis, goal setting, message formulation, media selection, and evaluation.

Hallahan et al. (2007) identify six key disciplines within strategic communication: management communication, marketing communication, public relations, technical communication, political communication, and social marketing campaigns. These disciplines collectively shape how government institutions communicate both internally and externally. In the context of social media, strategic communication requires not only content production but also alignment between organizational goals and communication practices.

However, previous studies indicate that many government institutions still struggle to implement communication strategically, particularly in digital environments. Social media is often used merely as an information dissemination tool rather than as a platform for engagement and interaction.

B. Social Media as a Public Communication Tool

Social media, as part of new media, enables interactive and participatory communication between government and citizens (Rahmanto, 2022). Unlike traditional media, social media provides opportunities for two-way communication, allowing governments to receive feedback, respond to public concerns, and involve citizens in policy processes. Bertot et al. (2012) highlight four key strengths of social media in the public sector: collaboration, participation, empowerment, and time flexibility. These characteristics position social media as a powerful tool for enhancing transparency and accountability in governance. Despite these potentials, the use of social media by government institutions often remains limited to one-way communication. This indicates a gap between the theoretical potential of social media and its practical implementation in the public sector.

C. Functional Use of Social Media

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To better understand how organizations utilize social media, Schlagwein and Hu (2013) categorize its use into five main functions: broadcasting, dialogue, collaboration, knowledge maintenance, and sociability. These categories provide a framework for analyzing the extent to which social media is used strategically.

Broadcasting refers to one-way information dissemination, while dialogue emphasizes two-way communication and interaction. Collaboration involves collective problem-solving and knowledge sharing, whereas knowledge maintenance focuses on information storage and retrieval. Sociability, on the other hand, relates to building social connections and communities. In the context of government communication, the dominance of one function over others reflects the maturity of social media usage. Institutions that rely heavily on broadcasting tend to underutilize the interactive potential of social media.

D. Government 2.0 and Social Media Maturity

Khan (2017) introduces a conceptual model of Government 2.0 that explains how governments utilize social media across three stages: information dissemination, mass collaboration, and social transactions. These stages represent different levels of maturity in digital governance. The first stage focuses on providing information to the public, while the second involves engaging citizens in collaborative processes. The third stage represents a more advanced level where social media facilitates actual service delivery and interaction between government and citizens.

Many government institutions, particularly in developing countries, are still positioned at the first stage, where social media is primarily used for broadcasting information. This indicates that the transition toward more participatory and interactive governance remains limited.

E. Bureaucratic Constraints in Digital Communication

The implementation of social media in government is often influenced by organizational structures and institutional dynamics. Criado and Villodre (2022) highlight that bureaucratic rigidity, lack of governance frameworks, and limited resources are significant barriers to the institutionalization of social media in public organizations.

Hierarchical decision-making processes and complex approval mechanisms can slow down communication flows, reducing the responsiveness of social media management. This is particularly problematic in digital environments, where speed and adaptability are essential.

As a result, there is often a mismatch between the dynamic nature of social media and the rigid structure of government bureaucracy. This tension becomes a critical issue in understanding the effectiveness of digital communication in the public sector.

F. Government Public Relations and Regulatory Framework

Government public relations (PR) plays a crucial role in managing communication between the state and its citizens. It involves disseminating information, managing public perception, and ensuring transparency (Cahyani, 2020). Unlike corporate PR, government PR operates within a non-commercial framework and is bound by ethical and regulatory constraints.

In Indonesia, the use of social media by government institutions is guided by the Regulation of the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform No. 83 of 2012. This regulation emphasizes the importance of strategic planning, audience analysis, and continuous evaluation in managing social media.

However, in practice, the role of government PR is often limited to technical communication functions rather than strategic management (Sani et al., 2020). This limitation affects how social media is utilized, often reducing it to a tool for information dissemination rather than a platform for public engagement.

IV. FINDINGS

This study is based on qualitative data collected through in-depth interviews with five employees of the Civil Service Police Unit (Satpol PP) of East Java Province who are directly involved in managing the institution's social media. The findings are organized into several key themes that reflect the characteristics, constraints, and dynamics of social media management within the bureaucratic context.

To provide an overview of the informants involved in this study, the following table is presented:

Table 1. Research Informants

No.	Informant	Position	Unit	Gender	Age
1	Informant 1	Publication Team Member	Fire Division	Male	32
2	Informant 2	Publication Team Member	General Affairs	Male	34
3	Informant 3	Publication Team Member	Planning Division	Female	31
4	Informant 4	Vice Head of PR Team	PR Unit	Male	39
5	Informant 5	Publication Tim member	Public Order Division	Male	34

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A. Characteristics of Social Media Use

The findings indicate that the use of social media in Satpol PP East Java is predominantly characterized by a broadcasting function, referring to one-way information dissemination with minimal public interaction. The content produced mainly consists of activity documentation, reports, and internal organizational agendas. This is evident from the following statements:

“Most of the content we produce is activity documentation; it has not yet reached the level of interaction with the public.” (Informant 2)

“It is more about publishing activities rather than engaging in two-way communication.” (Informant 3)

These findings suggest that social media has not been utilized as a dialogic platform but rather as a formal information channel. To further illustrate these characteristics, the following table summarizes the findings:

Table 2. Characteristics of Social Media Use

<i>Aspect</i>	<i>Findings</i>	<i>Evidence</i>
Content Type	Activity documentation	“Activity documentation”
Communication Pattern	One-way (broadcasting)	“Not yet interactive”
Public Engagement	Minimal	No active response to audience

The dominance of the broadcasting function indicates that the organization remains at an early stage of social media utilization, focusing primarily on information delivery rather than interaction or participation.

B. Bureaucratic Constraints in Content Production

One of the most significant findings of this study is the presence of bureaucratic constraints in the process of content production and publication. Each piece of content must go through multiple layers of approval involving different levels of authority within the organization. As explained by the informants:

“Content cannot be uploaded directly; it must first go through leadership approval.” (Informant 4)

“Everything has to go up the chain—from the team to the supervisors—before it can be posted.” (Informant 1)

This layered approval system results in delays in content publication and reduces the responsiveness of communication.

Table 3. Content Approval Process

<i>Stage</i>	<i>Actor</i>	<i>Role</i>
Content Creation	Media Team	Content production
Initial Review	Subdivision	Initial verification
Approval	Secretary	Administrative approval
Final Approval	Head of Agency	Final decision

This multi-layered process demonstrates that although social media is inherently dynamic, its management remains embedded within a rigid bureaucratic structure. Consequently, communication becomes slower and less relevant to real-time developments.

C. Organizational Capacity and Human Resources

The findings also reveal limitations in organizational capacity, particularly in terms of human resources. Most members of the social media team do not have a background in public relations or communication.

As stated by the informants:

“We are not actually from a PR background, so we learn as we go.” (Informant 1)

“Not everyone has communication skills; most of us come from different divisions.” (Informant 5)

“This is not our main job, so we handle it when we have time.” (Informant 2)

In addition, social media management is not considered a primary responsibility but rather an additional task alongside their main duties. These limitations in expertise and role clarity contribute to suboptimal social media management, both in terms of strategic planning and content execution.

D. Absence of Strategic Communication

The study finds that social media management in Satpol PP East Java is not guided by a structured strategic communication framework. There is no formal content planning, editorial calendar, or clearly defined communication objectives.

“There is no specific planning; we usually just follow ongoing activities.” (Informant 3)

“We post based on activities; there is no particular strategy.” (Informant 2)

These findings indicate that social media is not managed as part of a strategic communication effort but rather as a tool for documenting and disseminating activities.

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Table 4. Strategic Communication Indicator

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Condition</i>
Content Planning	Not available
Communication Objectives	Undefined
Evaluation	Not systematic
Audience Targeting	Not specified

The absence of a strategic approach reduces the effectiveness of communication, particularly in fostering public engagement.

E. Structural Tension in Digital Communication

The most significant finding of this study is the presence of structural tension between the dynamic nature of social media and the rigid characteristics of bureaucratic systems. Social media requires speed, flexibility, and responsiveness, whereas bureaucratic structures emphasize procedures, hierarchy, and control.

This tension is reflected in the informants' statements:

“Social media needs to be fast, but here the process is long.” (Informant 3)

“Sometimes the information is no longer relevant because it takes too long to process.” (Informant 4)

This mismatch results in suboptimal use of social media as a communication tool. The following table summarizes this structural tension:

Table 5. Structural Tension in Social Media Management

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>Digital Communication</i>	<i>Bureaucratic System</i>
Speed	Fast	Slow
Flexibility	High	Low
Decision-making	Decentralized	Hierarchical
Communication Flow	Real-time	Sequential

The incompatibility between these two systems emerges as the primary factor hindering effective social media management. This finding suggests that digital transformation in government institutions requires not only technological adoption but also organizational and structural change.

V. DISCUSSION

This study reveals that the practice of social media management in the Satpol PP of East Java Province remains at an early stage of digital communication utilization. The findings highlight the dominance of broadcasting functions, the absence of strategic communication, bureaucratic constraints, and structural tensions between digital communication and bureaucratic systems. This section discusses these findings in relation to the theoretical framework presented earlier.

A. Social Media Use Beyond Strategic Communication

The findings indicate that social media in Satpol PP East Java is not yet managed as part of a strategic communication framework. According to Hallahan et al. (2007), strategic communication involves the purposeful use of communication to achieve organizational goals, including building relationships with stakeholders. However, this study shows that social media use is largely reactive and activity-based rather than strategically planned.

The dominance of activity documentation suggests that communication efforts are not aligned with broader organizational objectives such as public engagement or trust-building. The absence of content planning, audience segmentation, and systematic evaluation further reinforces the conclusion that social media is being used as an administrative communication tool rather than a strategic instrument.

B. Broadcasting-Oriented Communication and Limited Public Engagement

Using the functional framework proposed by Schlagwein and Hu (2013), the findings demonstrate that social media use is concentrated in the broadcasting function, with limited development of dialogue, collaboration, or participatory communication. This indicates a gap between the theoretical potential of social media and its practical implementation. Bertot et al. (2012) emphasize that social media enables participation, collaboration, and citizen empowerment. However, in this case, such potential remains underutilized.

The lack of interaction also suggests that social media is not being used to foster two-way communication. As a result, public engagement remains low, limiting the role of social media as a platform for democratic communication.

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C. Institutional Constraints and Bureaucratic Rigidity

The findings confirm that bureaucratic structures significantly influence the effectiveness of social media management. Multi-layered approval processes and hierarchical decision-making create delays in content publication.

This aligns with Criado and Villodre (2022), who argue that bureaucratic rigidity and weak governance frameworks are key barriers to the institutionalization of social media in the public sector. In the context of Satpol PP East Java, bureaucracy not only slows down communication but also restricts flexibility in responding to real-time issues. Thus, organizational structure emerges as a critical factor shaping digital communication practices.

D. Human Resource Limitations and Informal PR Practices

Another important finding relates to the limited capacity of human resources involved in social media management. The absence of formal public relations backgrounds among team members indicates that communication functions are not professionally managed.

Within the framework of Government Public Relations, PR practitioners are expected to design communication strategies, manage public perception, and build relationships with stakeholders (Cahyani, 2020). However, as noted by Sani et al. (2020), government PR often functions only as a technical facilitator rather than a strategic actor.

Furthermore, the positioning of social media management as an additional task reflects the low organizational priority given to communication functions. This contributes to inconsistencies and a lack of focus in social media practices.

E. Social Media Maturity: Stuck at the Information Stage

Applying the Government 2.0 model (Khan, 2017), Satpol PP East Java can be categorized at the initial stage of information dissemination. At this level, social media is primarily used to deliver information rather than to facilitate interaction or collaboration.

The subsequent stages—mass collaboration and social transaction—are not evident in current practices. This suggests that digital transformation within the organization remains superficial and has not yet reached participatory levels.

This finding highlights that technological adoption alone is insufficient. Organizational change, cultural adaptation, and capacity building are necessary for more advanced digital governance.

F. Structural Tension as the Core Contribution

The most significant contribution of this study lies in identifying the structural tension between the dynamic nature of social media and the rigid characteristics of bureaucratic systems. Social media requires speed, flexibility, and responsiveness, whereas bureaucracy emphasizes procedures, hierarchy, and control. This tension results in the “bureaucratization” of social media, where digital platforms lose their inherent dynamism due to organizational constraints.

This finding contributes to the broader discourse on government communication by demonstrating that the challenges of social media management are not merely technological but fundamentally structural. Therefore, digital transformation in the public sector must be accompanied by bureaucratic reform.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that social media management in the Satpol PP of East Java Province is still characterized by a predominantly one-way communication approach, limited strategic planning, and significant bureaucratic constraints. Social media is primarily used as a tool for information dissemination rather than as a platform for interaction and public engagement.

The findings highlight three main issues: (1) the absence of strategic communication in social media management, (2) limited human resource capacity, and (3) structural barriers within bureaucratic systems. These factors collectively hinder the effectiveness of digital communication practices.

The study also identifies a fundamental tension between the dynamic nature of social media and the rigid structure of bureaucracy. This tension represents the core challenge in integrating digital communication within government institutions.

A. Theoretical Contribution

This research contributes to the literature on government communication by demonstrating that social media adoption in public institutions is shaped not only by technological factors but also by organizational structures and institutional dynamics.

B. Practical Implications

Practically, this study suggests the need for:

- Strengthening strategic communication planning
- Enhancing human resource capacity in public relations
- Simplifying bureaucratic procedures in content management

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C. Limitations and Future Research

This study is limited to a single institution and focuses on a specific organizational context. Future research may explore comparative studies across different government institutions or examine the role of leadership in shaping digital communication practices.

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